

Naturally Occurring Xanthenes from Terrestrial Flora

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Xanthenes isolated during the period 1980 to mid-1991 are tabulated under different classifications along with their plant sources. CMR data of xanthenes in general have also been incorporated. The importance of xanthenes as possible chemotherapeutic agents, has been discussed. In addition, the plant sources that are known to produce xanthenes upto now have been presented in a tabular form indicating the families to which they belong.

Xanthone (Dibenzo- γ -pyrone, 1) comprises an important section of oxygen heterocycles. The first naturally occurring xanthone is Gentisin (2), isolated from *Gentiana lutea*¹ in 1821. Till to date, a large number of naturally occurring xanthenes have been isolated from higher plants (Angiosperms), ferns, fungi and lichens.

The growing interest in this class of naturally occurring compounds in view of their interesting pharmacological properties as well as their importance in chemotaxonomy, has resulted voluminous work in this field. In the past few years although a number of articles on xanthenes²⁻¹⁸ appeared in literature in quick succession, it was thought pertinent to present a resumé on this subject covering all the literature of each class of phyto-xanthenes which were published during 1980 to mid-1991.

The botanical families Gentianaceae and Guttiferaceae still remain as the principal source of xanthenes having different oxygenation patterns. The occurrence of prenylated and the corresponding cyclised pyrano- and/or furanoxanthenes is still limited to the families Gentianaceae, Guttiferaceae and Moraceae. Besides these three families, xanthenes have been found to occur in the families Hypericaceae, Lythraceae, Leguminosae, Iridaceae, Polypodiaceae, Polygalaceae, Malpighiaceae, Hippocrateaceae, Flacourtiaceae, Sapotaceae, Convolvulaceae, Gramineae, Malvaceae, Bignoniaceae, Liliaceae and Anacardiaceae. It is interesting to note that the first two families (Hypericaceae and Lythraceae) have not been reported earlier to produce any xanthone derivatives. With a view to have an in-depth

picture, the different plants that have so far been found to produce xanthone are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—LIST OF FAMILIES, GENERA AND SPECIES KNOWN TO PRODUCE XANTHONES*

Genus	Species
Family 1 : Gentianaceae (800)	
<i>Swertia</i> (90)	<i>S. alata</i> , <i>S. angustifolia</i> , <i>S. bimaculata</i> , <i>S. chirata</i> , <i>S. connata</i> , <i>S. cordata</i> , <i>S. decussata</i> , <i>S. campestris</i> , <i>S. dilatata</i> , <i>S. devida</i> , <i>S. gracilescens</i> , <i>S. hookeri</i> , <i>S. iberica</i> , <i>S. japonica</i> , <i>S. lawii</i> , <i>S. milensis</i> , <i>S. mussotii</i> , <i>S. patens</i> , <i>S. paniculata</i> , <i>S. perfoliata</i> , <i>S. petiolata</i> , <i>S. perenii</i> , <i>S. purpurascens</i> , <i>S. perennis</i> , <i>S. pernennis</i> , <i>S. racemosa</i> , <i>S. randaiensis</i> , <i>S. swertopsis</i> , <i>S. tetrapetala</i>
<i>Centaurium</i> (30)	<i>C. erythraea</i> , <i>C. cachenlahuen</i> , <i>C. linari-folium</i> , <i>C. litterale</i> , <i>C. pulchellum</i>
<i>Erythraea</i> (50)	<i>E. centaurium</i>
<i>Gentiana</i> (425)	<i>G. acantis</i> , <i>G. alpina</i> , <i>G. angustifolia</i> , <i>G. asclepiadea</i> , <i>G. barbata</i> , <i>G. bellidifolia</i> , <i>G. bimaculata</i> , <i>G. bavarica</i> , <i>G. cruciata</i> , <i>G. purpurea</i> , <i>G. campestris</i> , <i>G. ciliata</i> , <i>G. clusii</i> , <i>G. corymbifera</i> , <i>G. favrotii</i> , <i>G. germanica</i> , <i>G. kochiana</i> , <i>G. lutea</i> , <i>G. pneumonanthe</i> , <i>G. marcaillouana</i> , <i>G. nivalis</i> , <i>G. radix</i> , <i>G. ramosa</i> , <i>G. schistocalyx</i> , <i>G. utriculosa</i> , <i>G. verna</i> , <i>G. pannonica</i> , <i>G. punctata</i>
<i>Macrocarpa</i> (30)	<i>M. glabra</i>
<i>Frasera</i> (8)	<i>F. albicaulis</i> , <i>F. albomarginata</i> , <i>F. carolinensis</i> , <i>F. speciosa</i> , <i>F. tetrapetala</i>
<i>Canscora</i> (30)	<i>C. decussata</i>
<i>Gentianopsis</i> (26)	<i>G. peludosa</i>
<i>Hopaea</i> (2)	<i>H. dichotoma</i>
<i>Halenia</i> (25)	<i>H. elliptica</i>
Family 2 : Guttiferaceae (900)	
<i>Garcinia</i> (400)	<i>G. buchanani</i> , <i>G. cowa</i> , <i>G. cruciata</i> , <i>G. hanburyi</i> , <i>G. mangostana</i> , <i>G. morella</i> , <i>G. rubra</i> , <i>G. quadrifaria</i> , <i>G. pedunculata</i> , <i>G. staudfii</i> , <i>G. thwaitesii</i>
<i>Calophyllum</i> (112)	<i>C. bracteatum</i> , <i>C. brasiliense</i> , <i>C. calaba</i> , <i>C. canum</i> , <i>C. fragrans</i> , <i>C. inophyllum</i> , <i>C. ramniflorum</i> , <i>C. sclerophyllum</i> , <i>C. scriblitifolium</i> , <i>C. thwaitesii</i> , <i>C. tomentosum</i> , <i>C. trapezifolium</i> , <i>C. wightianum</i> , <i>C. zeylancium</i>

Table—1 (Contd.)

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<i>Kielmeyera</i> (20)	<i>K. candidissima</i> , <i>K. corymbosa</i> , <i>K. coriacea</i> , <i>K. densiflora</i> , <i>K. excelsa</i> , <i>K. ferruginea</i> , <i>K. grandifolia</i> , <i>K. petiolaris</i> , <i>K. rupestris</i> , <i>K. speciosa</i> , <i>K. rubriflora</i>
<i>Rheedia</i> (—)	<i>R. brasiliensis</i> , <i>R. gardneriana</i> , <i>R. benthamiana</i>
<i>Tovomita</i> (60)	<i>T. brasiliensis</i> , <i>T. choisyana</i> , <i>T. excelsa</i> , <i>T. pyriformis</i> , <i>T. mangle</i>
<i>Mammea</i> (49)	<i>M. acuminata</i> , <i>M. africana</i> , <i>M. americana</i>
<i>Haploclathra</i> (4)	<i>H. leiantha</i> , <i>H. verticillata</i>
<i>Mesua</i> (3)	<i>M. ferrea</i> , <i>M. thwaitesii</i>
<i>Ochrocarpos</i> (25)	<i>O. odoratus</i>
<i>Caraipa</i> (12)	<i>C. densiflora</i>
<i>Vismia</i> (35)	<i>V. guaramirangae</i>
<i>Allanblackia</i> (8)	<i>A. floribunda</i>
<i>Cratogeomys</i> (12)	<i>C. celebicum</i> , <i>C. grandiflora</i> , <i>C. densiflora</i>
<i>Kayea</i> (4)	<i>K. stylosa</i>
<i>Symphonia</i> (21)	<i>S. globulifera</i>
<i>Lorostemon</i> (—)	<i>L. coelhoi</i> , <i>L. negrensis</i>
<i>Psorospermum</i> (—)	<i>P. febrifugum</i>

Family 3 : Moraceae (1000)

<i>Cudrania</i> (3)	<i>C. javanensis</i> , <i>C. tricuspidata</i>
<i>Maclura</i> (12)	<i>M. pomifera</i>
<i>Chlorophora</i> (12)	<i>C. tinctoria</i>

Family 4 : Hypericaceae (350)

<i>Hypericum</i> (300)	<i>H. androsaemum</i> , <i>H. aucheri</i> , <i>H. acutum</i> , <i>H. balearicum</i> , <i>H. calycinum</i> , <i>H. canariensis</i> , <i>H. chinense</i> , <i>H. ericoides</i> , <i>H. fumiferum</i> , <i>H. mysorensis</i> , <i>H. maculatum</i> , <i>H. montanum</i> , <i>H. nummularium</i> , <i>H. pulchrum</i> , <i>H. perforatum</i> , <i>H. sampsonii</i>
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Family 5 : Iridaceae (800)

<i>Iris</i> (300)	<i>I. dichotoma</i> , <i>I. ensata</i> , <i>I. florentina</i> , <i>I. pseudacorus</i> , <i>I. setosa</i>
<i>Belamcanda</i> (—)	<i>Belamcanda</i> sp.
<i>Crocus</i> (80)	<i>C. aureus</i>
<i>Pogonitis</i> (—)	All species

Family 6 : Leguminosae (13000)

<i>Hedysarum</i> (100)	<i>H. alpinum</i> , <i>H. caucasicum</i> , <i>H. denticulatum</i> , <i>H. semenovi</i> , <i>H. sericeum</i> , <i>H. obscurum</i>
<i>Dalbergia</i> (300)	<i>D. latifolia</i>
<i>Cassia</i> (450)	<i>C. occidentalis</i> , <i>C. reticulata</i>

Family 7 : Polygalaceae (700)

<i>Polygala</i> (475)	<i>P. arillata</i> , <i>P. macradenia</i> , <i>P. paenea</i> , <i>P. spectabilis</i> , <i>P. tenuifolia</i> , <i>P. triphylla</i>
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Family 8 : Lythraceae (475)

<i>Lawsonia</i> (1)	<i>L. inermis</i>
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Family 9 : Anacardiaceae (600)

<i>Mangifera</i> (30)	<i>M. indica</i>
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Family 10 : Polypodiaceae (7000)

<i>Athyrium</i> (180)	<i>A. mesosorum</i>
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Family 11 : Bignoniaceae (750)	
<i>Tabebuia</i> (100)	<i>T. guayacan</i>

Family 12 : Liliaceae (400)

<i>Anaemarrhena</i> (—)	<i>A. asphodeloides</i> , <i>A. rhizoma</i>
<i>Smilax</i> (30)	<i>S. glycyphylloides</i>

Family 13 : Malpighiaceae (—)

<i>Hiptage</i> (25)	<i>H. madagblota</i>
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Family 14 : Hippocrateaceae (225)

<i>Salacia</i> (10)	<i>S. prunoides</i>
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Family 15 : Flacourtiaceae (850)

<i>Flacourtia</i> (15)	<i>F. indica</i>
<i>Aphloia</i> (6)	<i>A. theaeformis</i> , <i>A. madagascariensis</i>

Family 16 : Sapotaceae (600)

<i>Madhuca</i> (85)	<i>M. utilis</i>
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Family 17 : Convolvulaceae (—)

<i>Cuscuta</i> (167)	<i>C. reflexa</i>
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Family 18 : Gramineae (4500)

<i>Cymbopogon</i> (60)	<i>C. afronardus</i>
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Family 19 : Malvaceae (1500)

<i>Urena</i> (6)	<i>U. lobata</i>
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Family 20 : Thymelaeaceae (500)

<i>Lasiosiphon</i> (25)	<i>L. eriocephalus</i> **
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*Figure in parenthesis indicates the total number of species available. **Ref. 203.

Chemotherapeutic value

In recent years, naturally occurring xanthenes have emerged out as an important class of organic compounds in view of their remarkable pharmacological and other biological activities. It has now been observed that a number of plant products which are in regular use as chemotherapeutic agents contain xanthenes as active constituents. Special mention may be made of the popular use of *Swertia chirata* and *Garcinia mangostana* as febrifuges.

Mangiferin (3), a xanthone-C-glycoside which is known to occur in a number of plants, has been found to exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activities. It shows monoamine oxidase inhibition, cardiostimulant, anticonvulsant and choleraic activities¹⁹⁻²². Pronounced anti-inflammatory activity has also been observed in mangiferin^{19,23,24}. Oral and topical compounds containing mangiferin are useful for the treatment of diseases caused by herpes virus^{25,26}. Mangiferin has been found to protect the liver of rats from high altitude hypoxia²⁷.

Total extract of *Swertia chirata* has been used in the Indian system of medicine as febrifuge as also to improve the liver function. It also enjoys much reputation as an antimalarial in traditional medicine. The Coded antimalarial drug AYUSH-64 by the Central Council for Research in Ayurveda and Siddha (Government of India) contains *Swertia chirata* as one of the ingredients²⁸. Simple xanthone (1,8-dihydroxy-3,5-dimethoxy) isolated from *S. chirata* has recently been found to exhibit antimalarial activity²⁹. The extract of the plant is known for therapeutic uses in the treatment of tuberculosis³⁰. Xanthones of *Chirata* are also reported to produce CNS depression²⁰. It is interesting to note that the total extract of *S. chirata* show significant antifeedant activity against jute semilooper, *Anomis sabulifera*³¹. This observation might be useful in connection with the cultivation and protection of jute.

Mangostin (4), the major constituent of *Garcinia mangostana*, showed activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, both normal and penicillin resistant strains³². The compound has also been found to show activity against *Tricophyton mentagrophytes*, *Microsporium gypseum* and *Epidermophyton floccosum*³³. Mangostin and some of its derivatives produced CNS depression characterised by ptosis, sedation, decreased motoractivity, potentiation of pentobarbital sleeping time and ether anaesthesia. Mangostin, isomangostin and mangostin triacetate produce pronounced anti-inflammatory activity both by i.p. and oral routes in rats tested by carragenin-induced hind-paw edema, cotton pellet implantation and granuloma pouch techniques. Mangostin also produce significant antiulcer activity in rats³⁴.

Norswertianolin (5), an *O*-glucoside of xanthone has been reported to produce antitubercular activity^{30,35,26}. The total extract of *Canscora decussata* which is used as a substitute for *S. chirata* has been shown to exhibit antitubercular activity in vitro³⁷. The extract of the plant has also been found to be useful in the treatment of certain mental disorders³⁸. It is worth mentioning that antitubercular activity of xanthones was first reported for 1,3,8-trihydroxy-derivatives.

It is interesting to note that the total xanthone-*O*-glucosides of *C. decussata*^{21,22} produce marked anti-psychotic effects whereas the xanthone-*O*-glycosides of *S. purpurescens* are known to produce signs of CNS depression in albino mice and rats^{36,39}. Xanthones of *Mammea americana* exhibit some

degree of growth inhibitory activity against sarcoma 180 tumour cell⁴⁰.

A number of xanthone derivatives, jacareubin and deoxyjacareubin, calophyllin B, mesuaxanthone A and B and euxanthone have been found to produce varying degree of CNS depression⁴¹.

Inhibition of Type A and Type B monoamine oxidases by a number of xanthones have been observed^{41,42,43}. Xanthones bearing 1,3-dihydroxy groups generally exhibit potent inhibition for both the types. The 3-*O*-glucosides of xanthones were much weaker than their corresponding genuine aglycones for both types of MAO.

Xanthone derivatives have been found to cause 60% inhibition of I₂-E mediated intestinal anaphylaxis and caused >95% inhibition of the passive cutaneous anaphylaxis reaction⁴⁴.

Total xanthones of *Veratilla baillonii* showed significant sedative action⁴⁵. CNS stimulant activity has also been observed in xanthone glycosides-mangiferin and lancerin⁴⁶. Recently hypoglycemic activity⁶⁵ is also observed in the xanthones of *Swertia chirata* Buch. Ham.

Classification

The xanthones isolated so far may be classified into five major groups. The simple oxygenated xanthones can again be subdivided into six groups according to the degree of oxygenation. The glycosides can also be grouped into *O*-glycosides and *C*-glycosides.

1. Simple oxygenated xanthones

- A. Mono-oxygenated
- B. Di-oxygenated
- C. Tri-oxygenated
- D. Tetra-oxygenated
- E. Penta-oxygenated
- F. Hexa-oxygenated

2. Xanthone glycosides

- A. *O*-Glycosides
- B. *C*-Glycosides

3. Prenylated and related xanthones

4. Xanthonolignoids
5. Miscellaneous

Simple oxygenated xanthones :

During the period (1980-mid 1991) under review as many as one hundred and twenty compounds have been isolated from fiftyeight plants belonging to the families Gentianaceae, Guttiferae, Hypericaceae and only in one case from Leguminosae. In these compounds, the highest degree of oxygenation has been observed to be six. Only two hexa-oxygenated compounds were known—one from

Polygalla macradenia and the other from *Canscora decussata*. Both the compounds are hexamethoxy derivatives. Four new hexa-oxygenated compounds have recently been isolated from Gentianaceae family. Interestingly, the oxygenation patterns of these compounds are different from those reported earlier. Further, Mandal and Chatterjee⁹³ were the first to isolate a dimeric xanthone from Angiosperms, viz. chiratanin (6) from *Swertia chirata* (Gentianaceae) which consists of two penta-oxygenated xanthone units attached by an ether linkage. The second dimer, ploiarixanthone¹⁹⁰ (7) was isolated from *Ploiarium alternifolium* and the third one, swertiabixanthone¹⁸⁸ (8) from *Swertia macrosperma*. The last two dimers have C-C linkage. Till now only these three dimeric xanthenes have been isolated from higher plants.

A list of all the simple oxygenated xanthenes is presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—LIST OF SIMPLE OXYGENATED XANTHONES

Sl. no.	Compd. (M.p. °C)	Source**
Mono-oxygenated		
1.	2-OH (240—41)	<i>Hypericum mysorense</i> ⁶³ <i>H. canariensis</i> ^{99,104} <i>H. ericoides</i> ⁹⁴ <i>H. balearicum</i> ⁶⁸ <i>Mammea acuminata</i> ⁸⁵

Table—2 (Contd)

2.	2-OMe (128—30)	<i>Vismia guaramirangae</i> ¹⁰⁵ <i>Mesua ferrea</i> ⁹¹ <i>Mammea acuminata</i> ⁸⁵
3.	4-OH (246)	<i>Mammea acuminata</i> ⁸⁵
Dioxygenated		
4.	1,7-(OH) ₂ (Euxanthone) (240—41)	<i>Hypericum canariensis</i> ^{101,104} <i>H. balearicum</i> ⁶⁸ <i>H. ericoides</i> ⁹⁴ <i>H. mysorense</i> ⁶³ <i>Garcinia xanthochymus</i> ⁵³ <i>Vismia guaramirangae</i> ¹⁰⁵ <i>Mammea acuminata</i> ⁸⁵ <i>Mesua ferrea</i> ⁹¹ <i>Calophyllum tomentosum</i> ⁸¹
5.	1-OH-7-OMe (132—33)	<i>Hypericum mysorense</i> ⁶³ <i>Mammea acuminata</i> ⁸⁵ <i>Vismia guaramirangae</i> ¹⁰⁵ <i>Mesua ferrea</i> ⁹¹
6*	2-OH-3-OMe (174—75)	<i>Hypericum mysorense</i> ⁶³
7.	1,5-(OH) ₂ (261)	<i>Mammea acuminata</i> ⁸⁵ <i>Mesua ferrea</i> ⁹¹ <i>Calophyllum tomentosum</i> ⁸¹
8.	1-OMe-5-OH	<i>M. acuminata</i> ⁸⁵ <i>Garcinia xanthochymus</i> ⁵³
9.	2-OMe-3-OH (233—35)	<i>Vismia guaramirangae</i> ¹⁰⁵ <i>Hypericum balearicum</i> ⁶⁸ <i>Mammea acuminata</i> ⁸⁵ <i>M. acuminata</i> ⁸⁵
10*	2,6-(OH) ₂ (310)	<i>M. acuminata</i> ⁸⁵
11*	2,5-(OH) ₂ (288—90)	<i>Hypericum canariensis</i> ^{99,104}
12.	2-OH-5-OMe (280—82)	<i>H. canariensis</i> ^{99,104}
13.	1-OH-6-OMe 3-Me-8-CO ₂ Me	<i>Aspergillus wentii</i> ⁷⁵
14.	1,6-(OH) ₂ -3-Me-8-CO ₂ Me	<i>A. wentii</i> ⁷⁵
15.	3',4'-Deoxyypsorospermin-4'-chloro-3'-ol	<i>Psorospermum febrifugum</i> ⁷⁸
Trioxxygenated		
16.	1-OH-3,5-(OMe) ₂ (173)	<i>Swertia mussotii</i> ⁴⁰
17.	1,3 (OH) ₂ -7-(OMe)	<i>S. petiolata</i> ^{1,93}
18.	2,3,4-(OMe) ₃ (149—50)	<i>Hypericum ericoids</i> ⁵⁵
19.	2-OH-3,4-(OMe) ₂ (186—89)	<i>H. sampsonii</i> ⁵⁶
20*	2,7-(OH) ₂ -3-OMe (299—300)	<i>Dalbergia latifolia</i> ⁷⁴
21.	1,5-(OH) ₂ -6-OMe	<i>Tovomita excelsa</i> ⁸⁹
22.	1 6-(OH) ₂ -5-(OMe) (Buchanaxanthone) (244)	<i>T. excelsa</i> ⁸⁹
23*	1-OMe-5,6-(OH) ₂ (218—23)	<i>T. excelsa</i> ⁸⁹
24*	1,7-(OH) ₂ -6-OMe (265—68)	<i>T. excelsa</i> ⁸⁹
25.	1,5,6-(OH) ₃ (Mesuaxanthone-B) (290)	<i>Mesua ferrea</i> ⁹¹
26.	1,5-(OH) ₂ -3-OMe (Mesuaxanthone-A) (273)	<i>M. ferrea</i> ⁹¹
27*	1,3-(OH) ₂ -2-OMe (176—78)	<i>Vismia guaramirangae</i> ¹⁰⁵
28*	1,5-(OH) ₂ -8-OMe (230—31)	<i>Vismia guaramirangae</i> ¹⁰⁵
29*	1,7-(OH) ₂ -4-OMe (239.5—240.5)	<i>Vismia guaramirangae</i> ¹⁰⁵
30*	3-OH-2,4-(OMe) ₂ (222—24)	<i>Hypericum canariensis</i> ¹⁰⁴
31.	2,3,4-(OMe) ₃	<i>Hypericum ericoides</i> ⁹⁴

Table—2 (Contd.)

32. 1-OH-3,5-(OMe) ₂	<i>Swertia patens</i> ⁹⁵
33. 1-OMe-2,8-(OH) ₂	<i>Haploclathra leiantha</i> ¹⁰⁸
34. 1,5-(OH) ₂ -3-OMe	<i>H. leiantha</i> ¹⁰⁸
35. 1,7-(OH) ₂ -3-OMe	<i>Swertia davida</i> ⁷⁶ <i>S. petiolata</i> ¹⁹⁸
36*. 2-(OMe)-3,6-(OH) ₂	<i>Hypericum reflexum</i> ¹⁹⁸
Tetraoxygenated	
37. 1,8-(OH) ₂ -3,5-(OMe) ₂	<i>Swertia patens</i> ⁹⁵ <i>Centaurium pulchellum</i> ⁹⁰ <i>Swertia paniculata</i> ⁵⁹ <i>S. japonica</i> ¹⁹² <i>S. milensis</i> ⁵² <i>S. petiolata</i> ¹⁹⁸ <i>S. tetrapetala</i> ⁵¹ <i>S. mussotii</i> ⁴⁹ <i>Comastoma pulmonarium</i> ¹⁷⁰ <i>Centaurium littorale</i> ¹⁰⁸
(185—87) (Swerschirin)	
38*. 1,7-(OH) ₂ -3,4-(OMe) ₂	<i>Veratrilla baillonii</i> ¹⁰⁷
(285—88)	
39. 1-OH-3,7,8-(OMe) ₃	<i>Swertia mussotii</i> ⁴⁹ <i>S. petiolata</i> ⁵⁰ <i>S. milensis</i> ⁵² <i>S. paniculata</i> ⁵⁹ <i>S. perfoliata</i> ⁸⁴ <i>Centaurium pulchellum</i> ⁹⁰ <i>Gentianopsis paludosa</i> ⁸⁶ <i>Comastoma pulmonarium</i> ¹⁷⁰
(151)	
40*. 1,3,5-(OMe) ₃ -8-OH	<i>Swertia mussotii</i> ⁴⁹ <i>Comastoma pulmonarium</i> ¹⁷⁰
(210)	
41. 1,3-(OH) ₂ -5,6-(OMe) ₂	<i>Haploclathra leiantha</i> ¹⁰⁸
(205—07)	
42. 1,6-(OMe) ₂ -2,8-(OH) ₂	<i>H. leiantha</i> ¹⁰⁸
43. 1,3-(OMe) ₂ -5,6-(OH) ₂	<i>H. leiantha</i> ¹⁰⁸
(Ferraxanthone)	
44. 1,5,6-(OMe) ₃ -3-OH	<i>H. leiantha</i> ¹⁰⁸
45. 1,3,5-(OH) ₃ -6-OMe	<i>H. leiantha</i> ¹⁰⁸
46*. 1,8-(OMe) ₂ -3,7(OH) ₂	<i>H. paniculata</i> ¹⁰⁹
(282—84)	
47. 1,8-(OH) ₂ -3,7-(OMe) ₂	<i>Swertia mussotii</i> ⁴⁹ <i>S. milensis</i> ⁵² <i>S. patens</i> ⁸⁹ <i>S. paniculata</i> ⁵⁹ <i>S. speciosa</i> ⁶² <i>Centaurium pulchellum</i> ⁹⁰ <i>Comastoma pulmonarium</i> ¹⁷⁰
(191)	
48. 1,7,8-(OH) ₂ -3-OMe	<i>Swertia mussotii</i> ⁴⁹ <i>S. paniculata</i> ⁵⁹
(Gentiakochianin)	
(226—27)	
49. 1,3,8-(OH) ₃ -5-(OMe)	<i>S. mussotii</i> ⁴⁹ <i>S. paniculata</i> ⁵⁹
(263—65)	
50. 1,5,8-(OH) ₃ -3-OMe	<i>S. perfoliata</i> ⁵³ <i>S. speciosa</i> ⁶² <i>S. paniculata</i> ⁵⁹ <i>S. japonica</i> ¹⁹²
(271)	
51. 1-OH-3,5,8-(OMe) ₃	<i>S. perfoliata</i> ⁵⁰ <i>S. paniculata</i> ⁵⁹ <i>S. petiolata</i> ¹⁹⁸ <i>Centaurium littorale</i> ¹⁰⁸
(214)	
52. 1-OH-2,3,5-(OMe) ₃	<i>Swertia tetrapetala</i> ⁵¹ <i>S. milensis</i> ⁶¹
(188)	
53. 2-OH-5,6,7-(OMe) ₃	<i>Hypericum ericoides</i> ⁵⁵
(206)	
54*. 1,6-(OH) ₂ -5,7-(OMe) ₂	<i>H. canariensis</i> ⁶⁰
(231—33)	
55. 1,7,8-(OMe) ₂ -3-OH	<i>Swertia paniculata</i> ⁵⁹
56. 1,5-(OH) ₂ -6,7-(OMe) ₂	<i>Tovomitia braziliensis</i> ⁶⁹
(249—51)	
57*. 1,6-(OMe) ₂ -2,5-(OH) ₂	<i>Garcinia thwaitesii</i> ⁷⁰
(207—08)	
58. 1,5-(OH) ₂ -2,3-(OMe) ₂	<i>Halenia elliptica</i> ⁷¹
(254—55)	
59. 1,7-(OH) ₂ -2,3(OMe) ₂	<i>H. elliptica</i> ⁷¹
(225—28)	
50. 1,6-(OH) ₂ -3,5-(OMe) ₂	<i>Centaurium linarifolium</i> ⁷³
(192—93)	

Table—2 (Contd.)

61*. 1,3,8-(OH) ₃ -2-OMe	<i>C. linarifolium</i> ⁷³
(262—64)	
62*. 3,8-(OH) ₂ -1,4-(OMe) ₂	<i>C. linarifolium</i> ⁷³
(170—72)	
63. 1,7-(OH) ₂ -3,8-(OMe) ₂	<i>Swertia petiolata</i> ¹¹⁰
(194)	
64*. 1,5,6-(OH) ₃ -3-OMe	<i>S. chirata</i> ⁹³
65. 1,3-(OH) ₂ -2,7-(OMe) ₂	<i>Veratrilla baillonii</i> ⁸⁸
66. 1-OH-3,5,6-(OMe) ₃	<i>Centaurium erythraea</i> ¹⁰²
(185—87)	
67*. 1,2,3-(OH) ₃ -5-OMe	<i>C. erythraea</i> ¹⁰⁸
(256—58)	
68*. 1,3-(OMe) ₂ -5,6-(OH) ₂	<i>Mesua ferrea</i> ⁹¹
(294—95)	
69*. 1,4-(OH) ₂ -3,5-(OMe) ₂	<i>Centaurium erythraea</i> ⁹²
(249—51)	
70. 1,8-(OH) ₂ -4,6-(OMe) ₂	<i>Erythraea centaurium</i> ¹⁰¹
(185—86)	
71. 1,8-(OH) ₂ -2,6-(OMe) ₂	<i>E. centaurium</i> ¹⁰¹
(188—90)	
72. 2-(OH)-5,6,7-(OMe) ₃	<i>Hypericum ericoides</i> ⁹⁴
73*. 1,3,8-(OH) ₃ -7-OMe	<i>Swertia iberica</i> ⁷⁷ <i>Comastoma pulmonarium</i> ¹⁷⁰
(Isogentiakochianin)	
(235—38)	
74. 1,3,6,7-(OH) ₄	<i>Gymnocarpium robertianum</i> ¹⁵⁸ (<i>G. jessoense</i>) <i>Diploschistes</i> ¹⁵⁷ (Lichen)
75*. 1,8-(OH) ₂ -3,6-(OMe) ₂	
(193—94)	
76*. 1,2,4-(OMe) ₃ -3-OH	<i>Psorospermum febrifugum</i> ¹⁵⁹ <i>P. ferruginum</i> ¹⁵⁹ <i>Almes glutinosa</i> ¹⁶³
77*. 1,3-(OH) ₂ -4,6-(OMe) ₂	
(192—94)	
78. 1,3,8-(OMe) ₃ -7-OH	<i>Haploclathra leiantha</i> ¹⁶⁴
79*. 1,3-(OH) ₂ -5,8-(OMe) ₂	<i>Swertia petiolata</i> ¹⁶⁵
(192,5—94,5)	
80*. 1-OMe-2,4,5-(OH) ₃	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁶ (BR-xanthone-B)
81*. 2,7-(OH) ₂ -3,4-(OMe) ₂	<i>Hypericum sublatum</i> ¹⁸⁰
82*. 1,3,7-(OH) ₃ -8-OMe	<i>Haploclathra paniculata</i> ¹⁸² (Haploxanthone)
83*. 1,3-(OH) ₂ -2,5-(OMe) ₂	<i>Bounetia dinizii</i> ¹⁹⁴
(249—52)	
84*. 2,4-(OH) ₂ -3,6-(OMe) ₂	<i>Hypericum reflexum</i> ¹⁹⁸
85*. 2,3,6-(OMe) ₃ -4-OH	<i>H. reflexum</i> ¹⁹⁸
86*. 1-OH-3 5-(OMe) ₂ -7-	<i>Hoppea fastigiata</i> ²⁰⁰ acetoxy
87*. 1,3,5,7-(OMe) ₄	<i>H. fastigiata</i> ²⁰⁰
88*. 1,7-(Acetoxy) ₂ -3,5-	<i>H. fastigiata</i> ²⁰⁰ (OMe) ₂
89*. 1-OH-3 6,8-(OMe) ₃	<i>Halenia elliptica</i> ²⁰¹
90*. 1,5-(OH) ₂ -3,8-(OMe) ₂	<i>Swertia chirata</i> ²⁰²
(191)	
Pentaoxygenated	
91*. 1,7-(OH) ₂ -3,4,8-	<i>S. mussotii</i> ⁴⁹
(OMe) ₃	
(217,5)	
92. 1-OH-2,3,4,7-(OMe) ₄	<i>S. tetrapetala</i> ⁵¹
(118—19)	
93*. 1,8-(OH) ₂ -3,4,6-	<i>Centaurium linarifolium</i> ⁷³
(OMe) ₃	
(225—27)	
94. 1-OH-3,4,7,8-(OMe) ₄	<i>Swertia paniculata</i> ⁵⁹
95*. 1,3,8-(OH) ₃ -2,6-(OMe) ₂	<i>Ixanthus viscosus</i> ⁵⁸
(231—33)	
96*. 1,8-(OH) ₂ -2,3,6-	<i>I. viscosus</i> ⁵⁸
(OMe) ₃	
(177—78)	
97*. 1,8-(OH) ₂ -3,4,5-	<i>Gentiana corymbifera</i> ⁶⁴
(OMe) ₃	
(231)	
98. 1-OH-2,3,4,5-(OMe) ₄	<i>Swertia milensis</i> ⁶¹ <i>Veratrilla baillonii</i> ⁸⁸ <i>Frasera tetrapetala</i> ⁶⁶ <i>F. speciosa</i> ⁹⁷
(155—56)	
99. 1,7-(OH) ₂ -2,3,4-	
(OMe) ₃	
(164—68)	

Table-2 (Contd.)

100*	1,5-(OH) ₂ -2,3,7-(OMe) ₃ (258)	<i>Halenia elliptica</i> ⁷¹
101*	1,2-(OH) ₂ -3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ (208)	<i>H. elliptica</i> ⁷¹
102.	1,4-(OH) ₂ -2,3,7-(OMe) ₃ (160-61)	<i>Veratrilba baillonii</i> ⁸⁸
103.	1,8-(OH) ₂ -3,4,6-(OMe) ₃ (236-37)	<i>Erythraea centaurium</i> ¹⁰¹
104*	1,2,3-(OH) ₃ -7,8-(OMe) ₂ (Swertiaiberin) (231-34)	<i>Swertia iberica</i> ⁷⁷
105.	1,8-(OH) ₂ -4,5,6-(OMe) ₃	<i>Gentiana corymbifera</i> ⁶⁴
106*	1,3-(OH) ₂ -2,4,7-(OMe) ₃	<i>Frasera tetrapetala</i> ⁹⁶
107.	1-OH-3,5,6,7-(OMe) ₄	<i>Centaurium erythraea</i> ¹⁰³
108.	1,4,8-(OH) ₃ -3,7-(OMe) ₂ (233-34)	<i>Tripterospermum lanceolatum</i> ¹⁰⁰
109.	1,3-(OH) ₂ -4,7,8-(OMe) ₃ (218-20)	<i>T. lanceolatum</i> ¹⁰⁰
110*	1,2,4-(OMe) ₃ -3,8-(OH) ₂	<i>Psorospermum febrifugum</i> ¹⁵⁹ <i>P. ferruginum</i> ¹⁵⁹
111.	1,4-(OH) ₂ -2,5,6-(OMe) ₃ (176-79)	<i>Almes glutinosa</i> ¹⁶³
Hexaoxygenated		
112*	1,8-(OH) ₂ -3,5,6,7-(OMe) ₄ (173-77)	<i>Centaurium littorale</i> ¹⁰⁸ <i>C. erythraea</i> ⁸⁶
113.	1,6,8-(OH) ₃ -3,5,7-(OMe) ₃ (213-15)	<i>C. erythraea</i> ⁶⁷
114*	1,7-(OH) ₂ -2,3,4,5-(OMe) ₄ (245)	<i>Halenia elliptica</i> ⁷¹
115*	1,6-(OH) ₂ -3,5,7,8-(OMe) ₄ (178-79)	<i>Centaurium linarifolium</i> ⁷³
116*	1,8-(OH) ₂ -2,3,4,6-(OMe) ₄ (168-70)	<i>C. linarifolium</i> ⁷²
117.	1-OH-3,5,6,7,8-(OMe) ₅	<i>C. littorale</i> ¹⁰⁶ <i>C. erythraea</i> ¹⁰²
Dimeric xanthone		
118*	1,1',8,8'-(OH) ₄ -3,3',5',6'-(OMe) ₄ -5,6'-bixanthonyl ether (Chiratanin) (152)	<i>Swertia chirata</i> ⁹³
119*	1,7-(OH) ₂ -8-[1',7'-(OH) ₂ -8'-xanthonyl]xanthone (Ploiari xanthone) (>360)	<i>Ploiarium alternifolium</i> ¹⁹⁰
120*	1,3,5,8-(OH) ₄ -7-[1',3',5',8'-(OH) ₄ -2'-xanthonyl]xanthone (Swertiabixanthone)	<i>Swertia macrosperma</i> ¹⁸⁸

* Indicates new compounds isolated during the period under review. **Superscript indicates reference number.

Xanthone glycosides :

As indicated earlier, xanthone glycosides may be

divided into *O*-glycosides and the *C*-glycosides depending on the nature of glycosidic linkage.

***O*-Glycosides :** *O*-Glycosides have been found to occur primarily in *Gentiana* and *Swertia*. These two genera belong to the family Gentianaceae. The other genera of Gentianaceae where *O*-glycosides of xanthenes are found to occur are *Hoppea* and *Canscora*. *Iris ensata* (Iridaceae) is the only higher plant other than those belonging to Gentianaceae which produces xanthone-*O*-glycosides. The most common oxygenation being 1,3,5,8-(tetraoxygenated). Six new oxygenation patterns, viz. 1,2,3,7 ; 1,3,6,8 ; 1,3,4,7 ; 1,2,5,6,8 ; 1,3,4,7,8 and 2,3,5,7,8 with glycosyl moiety at either 1-, 5-, 7- or 8-position have been encountered in the newly isolated xanthone-*O*-glycosides. *Veratrilba baillonii*, *Tripterospermum taiwanse* and the fern genus *Athyrium* have been found to produce the new oxygenation patterns. The only hexaoxygenated xanthone-*O*-glycoside has been reported from *Chrozophora prostrata*¹⁷².

There are six diglycosides involving the positions 6 : 8, 2 : 7 and 2 : 6. More than 50% of *O*-glycosides have the sugar moiety attached to position-1 of the xanthone nucleus which is difficult to explain in view of the vicinity of the carbonyl function as this might create strain. Two new *O*-glycosides-9 and 10 with sugar moiety in position-5 have recently been isolated from *Tripterospermum taiwanse* and *Swertia japonica* respectively. Both the plants belong to the family Gentianaceae. The only glycoside with sugar moiety attached to position-4 (11) was reported from *Cassia fistula*, family Leguminosae.

***C*-Glycosides :** Compared to *O*-glycosides the occurrence of *C*-glycosides is very much limited. This is particularly true in the case of *C*-glycosides of xanthone. The first *C*-glycosides of xanthone, mangiferin (3) was first isolated in 1908 from *Mangifera indica* (Anacardiaceae)¹¹¹. Mangiferin

occurs in a number of plants of Angiosperms. Its occurrence has also been reported in a number of ferns. Contrary to the previous findings that mangiferin is a congener of flavanoids, it has now been found to co-occur with polyoxygenated xanthenes.

A list of both *O*-glycosides and *C*-glycosides of xanthenes that have been isolated is presented in Table 3.

It is worth mentioning that dilatatin (12), the newly isolated xanthone-*C*-glycoside, is the first example of *C*-allosylated natural product.

Prenylated and related compounds :

From genetic aspect, the family Guttiferae appears to be interesting. It produces a large number of xanthenes having isopentenyl and geranyl substituents. This has been observed in twenty species belonging to ten genera. It is interesting to note that in case of gambogic acid (13), the geranyl substituent is cyclised whereas in the case of rubraxanthone (14), cowaxanthone (15) and its congeners the side chain is unfolded. Prenylated and the corresponding pyranoxanthenes

have also been reported to occur in Moraceae. Only two genera *Maclura* and *Cudrania* in Moraceae are known to produce such compounds. *Hypericum* is grouped in Guttiferae instead of separate family Hypericaceae which biosynthesises pyranoxanthone. A unique oxalactone dibenzoxanthone (16) has been isolated¹³¹ from the heart wood of *Tabebuia guayacana* belonging to the family Bignoniaceae. During the period under observation eighty new compounds in this class have been isolated. Most of the plants belonging to the families Guttiferae and Moraceae have been found to produce this type of new compounds.

The pyronoxanthone jacareubin (17) has been suggested as a 'Chemotaxonomic Marker' at the generic level in *Calophyllum*³ in view of the fact that in almost all the *Calophyllum* species that has been examined, the presence of the compound has been confirmed. However, it is worth recording that in some species of *Kielmeyera*, *Pentadesma* and *Mesua*, jacareubin also has been found to occur^{137,138}.

TABLE 3—LIST OF XANTHONE GLYCOSIDES

Sl. no.	Compd.		M.p. °C	Source**	
(A) <i>O</i>-glycosides					
Tri-oxygenated					
1*	1	3	7	293—94	<i>Gentiana lutea</i> ¹⁷²
	OH	OMe	<i>O</i> -prim		
2*	1	3	7	259—60	<i>G. lutea</i> ¹⁷²
	<i>O</i> -prim	OMe	OH		
3.	1	2	3	—	<i>Polygala triphylla</i> ⁸³
	<i>O</i> -glu	OH	OMe		
4.	1	2,3		—	<i>P. triphylla</i> ⁸³
	<i>O</i> -glu	OCH ₂ O			
5*	1		3	240	<i>Chrozophora prostrata</i> ¹⁷⁸
	<i>O</i> -xylo(1-6)-glu	OMe	OMe		
Tetra-oxygenated					
6.	1	3	7	—	<i>Swertia paniculata</i> ⁸⁹
	<i>O</i> -glu	OMe	OMe		
7.	1	3	7	—	<i>S. paniculata</i> ⁸⁹
	<i>O</i> -glu	OMe	OH		
8.	1	3	7	—	<i>S. paniculata</i> ⁸⁹
	<i>O</i> -glu	OMe	OMe		
9.	1	3	5	—	<i>S. paniculata</i> ⁸⁹
	<i>O</i> -glu	OMe	OMe		
10*	1	3	5	259	<i>Swertia japonica</i> ¹¹³
	OH	OMe	<i>O</i> -glu		
11*	1	3	5	240	<i>Chrozophora prostrata</i> ¹⁷³
	<i>O</i> -glu	OMe	OMe		
12.	1	3	5	—	<i>Swertia japonica</i> ¹¹³
	OH	OMe	OH		
13.	1	3	5	—	<i>S. japonica</i> ¹¹³
	OH	OH	OH		<i>S. randaiensis</i> ¹¹⁸
14.	1	3	7	—	<i>S. petiolata</i> ¹¹⁰
	OH	OMe	OH		

Table-3 (Contd.)

15.	1	3	5	8	215-17	<i>S. angustifolia</i> ¹¹⁴
16.	OH	OMe	OH	<i>O</i> -glu	163	<i>S. connata</i> ¹¹⁵
17.	1	3	7	8	205-10	<i>Gentiana barbata</i> ¹¹⁶
18.	OH	OH	OMe	<i>O</i> -glu	—	<i>S. hookeri</i> ¹¹⁷
19.	1	3	7	8	150-52	<i>S. iberica</i> ¹¹⁸
20*.	<i>O</i> -prim	OMe	OMe	OMe	—	<i>S. iberica</i> ¹¹⁸
21.	1	3	7	8	—	<i>Gentiana barbata</i> ¹¹⁸
22*.	OH	OMe	OH	OH	—	<i>Asplenium adiantum-nigrum</i> ¹²⁰
23*.	1	3	7	8	—	<i>A. adiantum-nigrum</i> ¹²¹
24*.	OH	OMe	OMe	<i>O</i> -glu	—	<i>Veratrilba baillonii</i> ¹²²
25*.	1	3	7	8	—	<i>Helenia elliptica</i> ¹⁶³
26*.	OH	OMe	OMe	OH	—	<i>Comastoma pulmonarium</i> ¹⁷⁰
27*.	1	3	5	7	239-43	<i>Helenia elliptica</i> ¹⁶⁵
28.	OH	OMe	OH	OMe	265	<i>Swertia petiolata</i> ¹⁹³
29*.	1	3	5	7	203	<i>S. japonica</i> ¹⁹²
30.	OH	OMe	OH	<i>O</i> -prim	—	<i>Halenia elliptica</i> ²⁰¹
31.	<i>O</i> -prim (Ellipticoside)	OMe	OMe	OMe	263-65	<i>Gymnocarpium robertianum</i> ¹⁶³
32*.	1	2	5	7	—	<i>Iris florentina</i> ¹²³
33*.	OH	OMe	OH	OH	—	<i>Tripterospermum taiwanense</i> ⁹⁸
34*.	1	3	4	7	217	<i>Cassia fistula</i> ¹⁷⁸
35*.	OH	OMe	<i>O</i> - α -L rhamnosyl (1 2)- <i>O</i> - β -D- glucopyrano- side	OMe	OH	
36*.	Heliniaside				—	<i>Helenia elliptica</i> ¹⁶³
37.	Trimethoxyheliniaside				—	<i>H. elliptica</i> ¹⁶³
38.	Hexa-oxygenated					
39*.	1	3	5	6	270	<i>Chrozophora prostrata</i> ¹⁷³
40.	<i>O</i> -rhamnogluc	OMe	OMe	OMe	OMe	
(B) C-glycosides						
41.	1	2	3	5	—	<i>Iris florentina</i> ¹²³
42.	OH	C-glu	OMe	OMe	—	<i>Iris florentina</i> ¹²³
43.	1	2	3	5	272	<i>Hymenophyllum dilatatum</i> ¹⁸¹
44.	OH	C-glu	OH	OH	270-71	<i>Swertia chirata</i> ⁹³
45.	1	2	3	6		<i>Cratoxylum pruniflorum</i> ¹⁷⁸
46.	OH	C-glu	OH	OH		

*Indicates new compounds isolated during the period under review. **Superscript indicates reference number.

A list of prenylated xanthones and related compounds that have been isolated during the period under review, is presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—PRENYLATED AND RELATED XANTHONES (18—96)

(Structures of compounds are given at the end of the Table)

Compd. no.	Name of the Compd. (M.p. °C)	Source*
18	Garcinon-A (224—25)	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ^{124,125}
19	Garcinone-B (190—92)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ^{124,125}
20	Garcinone-C (216—18)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ^{124,125}
21	Garcinone-D (202—04)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹²⁵
22	5,9-Dihydroxy-8-methoxy-2,2-dimethyl-7-(3-methyl-but-2-enyl)-2 <i>H</i> , 6 <i>H</i> -pyrano-[3,2- <i>b</i>]xanthone-6-one (156—57)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹²⁵
23	1,3,5-(OH) ₃ -4,8-bis (3,3-dimethylallyl) xanthone (168—69)	<i>G. quadrifaria</i> ¹²⁷
24	Rheediaxanthone-A (245—47)	<i>G. staudfi</i> ¹²⁷
14	Rubraxanthone (210)	<i>G. pyrifera</i> ¹²⁸
25	Isocowanin (160)	<i>G. pyrifera</i> ¹²⁸
26	Isocowanol Amorphous	<i>G. pyrifera</i> ¹²⁸
27	Nervosaxanthone Amorphous	<i>G. pyrifera</i> ¹²⁸
28	Isorheedia-xanthone-B	<i>G. nervosa</i> ¹²⁸ <i>G. pyrifera</i> ¹²⁸
29	4',5'-Dihydro-1,5-dihydroxy-6',6'-dimethyl-pyrano(2',3' : 6,7)-4'',4'',5''-trimethylfurano(2'',3'', 3,4)xanthone (194—95)	<i>Rheedia brasiliensis</i> ¹²⁹
30	1,3,5-Trihydroxy-6',6'-dimethyl-pyrano(2',3' : 6,7)-4-(1,2-dimethyl prop-2-enyl)xanthone (188—89)	<i>R. brasiliensis</i> ¹²⁹
31	1,3,5,6-Tetrahydroxy-4-(1,1-dimethyl prop-2-enyl)-7-(3-methyl-but-2-enyl)xanthone (173—74)	<i>R. brasiliensis</i> ¹²⁹
32	Macluraxanthone (181—82)	<i>R. banthamiana</i> ¹³⁰
33	Manglixanthone	<i>R. banthamiana</i> ¹³⁰
34	Rheediaxanthone-B (208—11)	<i>R. banthamiana</i> ¹³⁰
35	Rheediaxanthone-C (260—63)	<i>R. banthamina</i> ¹³⁰
36	New xanthone (208—10)	<i>R. gardneriana</i> ⁵⁴
37	New xanthone (216—18)	<i>R. gardneriana</i> ⁵⁴
38	1,3,5-(OH) ₃ -2,4-bis (3-methylbut-2-enyl) xanthone (8-Deoxygartanin) (162—64)	<i>R. gardneriana</i> ¹³²

Table—4 (Contd.)

39	1,5-(OH) ₂ -6',6'-Dimethyl-2 <i>H</i> -pyrano (2',3',3,2)-6'',6''-dimethyl-2 <i>H</i> -pyrano (2'',3'',6,7)xanthone (Pyranojacareubin) (259.5—260.5)	<i>R. gardneriana</i> ¹³²
40	1,5,6-(OH) ₃ -6',6'-Dimethyl-2 <i>H</i> -pyrano (2',3' : 3,2)-7-(3-methylbut-2-enyl)xanthone (Prenyljacareubin) (218—20)	<i>Rheedia gardneriana</i> ¹³²
41	Cudraxanthone-A (212—16)	<i>Cudrania tricuspidata</i> ¹³³
42	Cudraxanthone-B (163—67)	<i>C. tricuspidata</i> ¹³³
43	Cudraxanthone-C (Powder)	<i>C. tricuspidata</i> ¹³³
44	1,5,6-Trihydroxy-6',6'-dimethyl-2 <i>H</i> -pyrano-(2',3' : 3,2)-4-(3,3-dimethyl-prop-2-enyl) xanthone (V ₁) (214—15)	<i>Vismia guineensis</i> ¹³⁴
45	1,5,6-Trihydroxy-2,4-di(3,3-dimethyl-prop-2-enyl)xanthone (V _{1a}) (176—79)	<i>V. guineensis</i> ¹³⁴
46	1,5,6-Trihydroxy-7-methoxy-6',6'-dimethyl-2 <i>H</i> -pyrano (2',3' : 3,2)-4-(3,3-dimethylprop-2-enyl)xanthone (V ₂) (210—13)	<i>V. guineensis</i> ¹³⁴
47	1,5,6-Trihydroxy-7-methoxy-2,4-di-(3,3-dimethylprop-2-enyl)xanthone (V _{2a}) (170—73)	<i>V. guineensis</i> ¹³⁴
48	1,3,5-Trihydroxy-2-(3-methyl-but-2-enyl)xanthone	<i>Calophyllum tomentosum</i> ¹³⁵
49	Calozeyloxanthone (236)	<i>C. zeylanicum</i> ¹³⁶
50	Zeyloxanthone (137)	<i>C. zeylanicum</i> ¹³⁶
51	Hypericanarin (222—24)	<i>Hypericum canariensis</i> ¹³⁷
52	Gerontoxanthone-A (236—38)	<i>Cudrania cochinchinensis</i> ¹³⁷
53	Gerontoxanthone-B (216—18)	<i>Cudrania cochinchinensis</i> ¹³⁷
54	Gerontoxanthone-C (204—06)	<i>Cudrania cochinchinensis</i> ¹³⁷
55	Gerontoxanthone-D (300)	<i>Cudrania cochinchinensis</i> ¹³⁷
56	Calothwaitesixanthone (169—72)	<i>Calophyllum thwaitesii</i> ¹³⁴
57	Thwaitesixanthone (221—24)	<i>Calophyllum thwaitesii</i> ¹³⁴
58	6-Deoxy-γ-mangostin (171—74)	<i>Calophyllum thwaitesii</i> ¹³⁴
59	Thwaitesixanthoneol (231)	<i>Calophyllum walkeri</i> ¹³⁵
60	Dimethyl calaxanthone (85)	<i>Calophyllum walkeri</i> ¹³⁵ <i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ¹³⁰

Table—4 (Contd.)

Table—4 (Contd.)

61	2'-Isopropyl-3-hydroxydihydrofuranodemethylcalabaxanthone	<i>Calophyllum walkeri</i> ¹⁵⁵
62	1,5,8-Trihydroxy-3-methoxy-2-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)xanthone	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ¹⁵⁸
63	Mangostin (180—82)	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
64	Gartanin (170—72)	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
65	γ-Mangostin (207—11)	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
66	β-Mangostin (176—80)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
67	1-Isomangostin (245—49)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
68	3-Isomangostin (155—50)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
69	3-Isomangostin hydrate (180—82)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
70	1-Isomangostin hydrate (255—57)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
71	Calabaxanthone (170—72)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
72	2-(γ,γ-Dimethylallyl)-1,7-dihydroxy-3-methoxyxanthone	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
73	2,8-Bis(γ,γ-dimethylallyl)-1,3,7-trihydroxyxanthone (163—70)	<i>G. mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁰
74	BR-xanthone-A	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ¹⁶⁶
75	1,5,8-Trihydroxy-3-methoxy-2-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)xanthone (193—95)	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ¹⁷¹

76	1,6-Dihydroxy-3-methoxy-2-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)xanthone (> 240)
77	New xanthone (212—13)
78	Alvaxanthone
79	Osajaxanthone (248)
80	6-Deoxyjacarubine (214—15)
81	Tovoxanthone (226)
82	Garcigerrin-A
83	Garcigerrin-B
84	2-(1',1'-Dimethylprop-2'-enyl), 1,4,5-trihydroxy-9 <i>H</i> -xanthone-9-one
85	Gerontoxanthone-E (136—38)
86	Gerontoxanthone-G (203—05)
87	Gerontoxanthone-H (175—77)
88	Gerontoxanthone-I (178—80)
89	Morusignins-A
90	Morusignins-B
91	Morusignins-C
92	Morusignins-D
93	Cudraxanthone-E
94	Cudraxanthone-F
95	Cudraxanthone-G
96	New xanthone

<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> ¹⁷¹
<i>Rheedia gardneriana</i> ⁵⁴
<i>Maclura aurantiaca</i> ¹⁸¹
<i>Maclura aurantiaca</i> ¹⁸¹
<i>Maclura aurantiaca</i> ¹⁸¹
<i>Maclura aurentiaca</i> ¹⁸¹
<i>Garcinia gerrardii</i> ¹⁸⁵
<i>Garcinia gerrardii</i> ¹⁸⁵
<i>Garcinia gerrardii</i> ¹⁸⁵
<i>Cudrania cochinchinensis</i> ¹⁸⁶
<i>Morus insignis</i> ¹⁹⁵
<i>Cudrania tricuspidata</i> ¹⁹⁶
<i>Cudrania tricuspidata</i> ¹⁹⁶
<i>Cudrania tricuspidata</i> ¹⁹⁶
<i>Hypericum reflexum</i> ¹⁹⁸

MANDAL, DAS & JOSHI : NATURALLY OCCURRING XANTHONES FROM TERRESTRIAL FLORA

Table-4 (Contd.)

(45) R = H

(47) R = OMe

(46)

(48)

(49)

(50)

(51)

(54) R =

(55) R = OMe

(52)

(53)

(56)

(57) R = CH₃

(59) R = CH₂OH

(58)

(60)

(61)

(62) R₁ = OMe, R₂ = H

(64) R₁ = OH, R₂ =

Table-4 (Contd.)

(63)

(65) $R_1 = R_2 = OH$

(66) $R_1 = R_2 = OMe$

(67) $R =$

(70) $R =$

(68) $R =$

(69) $R =$

(71)

(72) $R_1 = OMe, R_2 = R_4 = H, R_3 = OH$

(73) $R_1 = R_3 = OH, R_2 = H, R_4 =$

(76) $R_1 = OMe, R_2 = OH, R_3 = R_4 = H$

(74)

(75)

(77)

(81)

(85)

$R_1 = R_3 = OH, R_2 = H$

$R_1 = R_3 = H, R_2 = OH$

(82)

(84)

*Superscript indicates reference number.

TABLE 5—STRUCTURES OF XANTHONOLIGNOIDS (97–107)
 (Structures of compounds are given at the end of the Table)

Compd. no.	Compd. (M.p. °C)	Source*
97	Kielcorin (245–46)	<i>Kielmeyera species</i> ¹⁸⁹ <i>Psorospermum febrifugum</i> ¹⁸⁴
101	Cadensin D (239–40)	<i>Hypericum canariensis</i> ¹⁴¹ <i>Psorospermum febrifugum</i> ¹⁸⁴
102	Isocadensin D (278–79)	<i>P. febrifugum</i> ¹⁸⁴
103	Isocadensin D monoacetate (240–41)	<i>P. febrifugum</i> ¹⁸⁴

Table-5 (Contd.)

104	Cadensin F (237–39)	<i>P. febrifugum</i> ¹⁸⁴
106	Cadensin G (265–66)	<i>P. febrifugum</i> ¹⁸⁴
105	6-Hydroxy isocadensin F (256–57)	<i>P. febrifugum</i> ¹⁸⁴
100	Cadensin C	<i>Vismia guarimirangae</i> ¹⁴⁰
98	Cadensin A	<i>Caraipa densiflora</i> ¹⁸⁹
99	Cadensin B	<i>Caraipa densiflora</i> ¹⁸⁹
107	New compound	<i>Hypericum reflexum</i> ¹⁸⁸

* Superscript indicates reference number.

Xanthonolignoids :

Xanthonolignoids (Table 5) are a relatively rare group of natural products. Castelao *et al.*¹³⁹ were the first to isolate three xanthonolignoids, kielcorin (97) from *Kielmeyera* species¹³⁹ and cadensin A (98) and B (99) from *Caraipa densiflora*¹³⁹. Monache *et al.*¹⁴⁰ isolated the fourth xanthonolignoid, cadensin C (100) from *Vismia guaramirangae*¹⁴⁰. The fifth xanthonolignoid, cadensin D (101) was isolated by Cardona *et al.*¹⁴¹ from *Hypericum canariensis*¹⁴¹. Another five new xanthonolignoids (102—106) have recently been obtained from *Psorospermum febrifugum*¹⁸⁴. Recently xanthonolignoid (107) has been isolated from *Hypericum reflexum*¹⁹⁸.

All the eleven xanthonolignoids are very much close in skeletal patterns, structure of the compounds have been settled mainly by spectral studies and by comparison with the parent compound kielcorin (97). In addition to uv, ir, pmr and mass spectrometry, CMR chemical shifts of kielcorin was studied by Castelao *et al.*¹⁸⁹ to confirm the structure (Table 22).

Compounds 97, 101 and 107 are 2,3,4-oxygenated, 98, 99, 100, 102, 103 and 104 are 2,3,4,8-oxygenated, 106 is 3,4,6,8-oxygenated and the only xanthonolignoid 105 has got 2,3,4,6,8-pentaoxygenation pattern in the xanthone skeleton. The *trans* relation of the dioxane protons was deduced from their axial-axial coupling constant and the *para*-relation of the phenolic OH with respect to the side-chain by a negative Gibbs test.

Biosynthesis of kielcorin (97) and cadensin-D (101) has been considered to occur from 3,4-dihydroxy-2-methoxyxanthone through a radical coupling process with coniferyl alcohol and syringenin, respectively, like the postulated biosynthesis of flavonolignoids¹⁴² and coumarinolignoids¹⁴³. Recently Pinto *et al.*¹⁴⁴ have confirmed the structure of the natural kielcorin (97) by synthesis from salicylic acid, pyrogallol and coniferyl alcohol.

Besides these compounds, some xanthenes with unusual substitutions have been isolated from different plant sources including lichens which could not be classified in the usual manner. These compounds have been grouped as 'Miscellaneous' (Table 6).

TABLE 6—LIST OF MISCELLANEOUS XANTHONES (108—120)

(Structures of compounds are given at the end of the Table)

Compd. no.	Compd. (M.p. °C)	Source*
108	8-Hydroxy-6-methyl xanthone-1-carboxylate	<i>Monilinia fruticola</i> ¹⁵²
109	Actinoplanone-A	<i>Actinoplanes</i> Sps. ¹⁶⁷
110	2,3-Methylenedioxy xanthone (192)	<i>Hypericum mysorense</i> ¹⁷⁴
111	7-Carboxyl-1,8-dihydroxy-3,5-dimethoxy xanthone	<i>Saponaria vaccaria</i> ¹⁸⁷
112	Saxanthone (198—200)	<i>Saponaria vaccaria</i> ¹⁸⁹

Table—6 (Contd.)

113	Euxanmodin A (>360)	<i>Ploiarium alternifolium</i> ¹⁹⁰
114	Euxanmodin B (290)	<i>Ploiarium alternifolium</i> ¹⁹⁰
115	Mazaltanone	<i>Polygala nitida</i> ¹⁹¹
116	1-O-Methyl mazaltanone	<i>Polygala nitida</i> ¹⁹¹
117	7-Methoxy-1-O-methyl mazaltanone	<i>Polygala nitida</i> ¹⁹¹
118	6-O-Methyl arthothelin	<i>Dimelaena lichen</i> ¹⁹⁷
119	1,3,6-Tri-O-methyl arthothelin	<i>Dimelaena lichen</i> ¹⁹⁷
120	Mangicrocin	<i>Saffron</i> ¹⁷⁹

Table—6 (Contd.)

* Superscript indicates reference number.

CMR spectral studies of xanthenes

No comprehensive study of the CMR of xanthenes has been published as yet although voluminous data have been reported. It was therefore decided to compile the data of each class of xanthone and report in the present review.

Idris *et al.*¹⁴⁵ studied the chemical shifts of individual carbon atoms of xanthenes by comparison of the experimental and calculated values. The calculated values for the aromatic carbon atoms were obtained from data for either xanthone or benzene (δ 129 ppm) by assuming additivity of substituent effects (Table 7).

TABLE 7—CMR SUBSTITUENT EFFECTS (IN PPM) IN SUBSTITUTED BENZENES^{146,147}

Substituent	Position			
	C-1	ortho	meta	para
OH	+26.9	-12.7	+1.4	-7.3
OMe	+31.4	-14.4	+1.0	-7.7
COPh	+ 9.4	+ 1.7	-0.2	+3.6
Me	+ 8.9	+ 0.7	-0.1	-2.9
OPh	+29.2	- 9.4	+1.6	-5.1

The chemical shifts of the substituted xanthone [1,3,6,7-tetramethoxy- (121), 1,7-dihydroxy-3,6-dimethoxy- (122), 1,7-allyloxy-3,6-dimethoxy- (123), 1,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-2,8-allyl- (124)] in Table 8 were computed from the experimental chemical shifts of xanthenes and the incremental values of the substituent shown in Table 7. The calculated and observed

chemical shifts were close enough in most cases to allow unambiguous assignments of carbon signals. The xanthone carbonyl group resonates in the range 174—182.2 ppm. Within this range the presence of a hydrogen bonded 1-hydroxyl group at C₁ showed signal at 179—182 ppm whereas the loss of this intramolecular hydrogen bonding on *O*-methylation or *O*-allylation caused the carbonyl resonance to move upfield by 5 ppm.

Frahm *et al.*^{148,149} studied CMR spectra of some important hydroxy- and methoxyxanthone derivatives (Tables 9—12). Effects of hydroxylation on carbonyl carbon shift and the methylation of hydroxy group and the corresponding shift increments which are of diagnostic value have been reported. The assignments of the various carbon signals of different naturally occurring complex xanthone molecules have become easier from the above information.

TABLE 8—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (ppm) OF COMPOUNDS 121—124

Compd. no.		C-1	C-2	C-3	C-4	C-5	C-6	C-7	C-8	C-9	C-4a	C-8a	C-9a	C-10a	OMe
121	Cal.	159.1	95.0	167.0	95.8	104.5	153.1	140.8	113.3		158.2	115.7	99.9	151.5	56.7
	Found	161.6	92.6	164.1	94.9	98.8	150.6	145.6	105.7	174.0	159.9	115.8		146.4	56.1 55.5
122	Cal.	154.6	96.7	167.4	96.2	104.9	153.3	136.3	115.0		158.6	115.7	101.6	149.5	56.3
	Found	157.2	96.6	165.7	92.3	99.8	155.3	144.5	107.7	179.2	162.5	112.8	102.6	151.0	56.0
123	Cal.	159.1	95.0	167.0	95.8	104.5	153.1	140.8	113.3		158.2	115.7	99.9	151.5	56.3
	Found	160.7	93.0	164.2	96.4	99.1	154.9	145.5	107.8	174.4	159.8	116.1	151.0	151.0	55.0
124	Cal.	155.3	105.6	168.1	96.1	102.1	153.3	137.0	123.9		155.7	116.4	101.5	149.8	56.3
	Found	155.5		163.5	88.6	97.2	151.6		125.5	182.2	160.0	109.6		140.6	55.8

Compd. no.		—CH ₂ —	=CH—	=CH ₂
122	Cal.	80.2	132.6	118.5
	Found	70.0	132.9	117.8
124	Cal.	30.3	136.8	114.8
	Found	26.4	136.3	114.3

Incremental values for methyl group are used as an approximation for allyl group

TABLE 10—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (ppm) OF HYDROXYXANTHONES

Sl. no.	C-1	C-2	C-3	C-4	C-4a	C-4b
1.	125.92	124.28	135.44	118.10	155.55	155.61
2.	160.98	110.16	137.45	107.18	155.74	155.54
3.	108.58	153.91	124.47	119.35	149.19	155.57
4.	127.96	114.08	164.01	102.16	157.57	155.38
5.	115.25	124.12	120.21	146.64	145.23	155.35
6.	162.91	98.16	165.90	94.10	157.39	144.88
7.	162.93	98.14	165.78	94.09	157.28	157.42
8.	162.88	97.99	165.16	93.96	157.42	149.03
9.	162.81	97.87	165.61	93.76	157.53	155.47
10.	162.18	98.56	166.55	94.35	157.44	146.10
11.	162.94	97.89	165.14	93.95	157.38	150.98
12.	162.66	97.73	164.71	93.64	157.39	148.01
13.	161.94	97.17	167.09	92.75	157.71	143.29
14.	161.89	97.25	166.94	92.78	157.22	150.89
15.	161.86	107.68	163.89	93.48	156.33	

TABLE 9—SUBSTITUTION PATTERN OF HYDROXYXANTHONE (125)

Sl. no.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	R ⁵	R ⁶	R ⁷	R ⁸
1.	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
2.	OH	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
3.	H	OH	H	H	H	H	H	H
4.	H	H	OH	H	H	H	H	H
5.	H	H	H	OH	H	H	H	H
6.	OH	H	OH	H	H	H	H	H
7.	OH	H	OH	H	OH	H	H	H
8.	OH	H	OH	H	H	OH	H	H
9.	OH	H	OH	H	H	H	OH	H
10.	OH	H	OH	H	H	H	H	OH
11.	OH	H	OH	H	OH	OH	H	H
12.	OH	H	OH	H	H	OH	OH	H
13.	OH	H	OMe	H	H	H	OH	OH
14.	OH	H	OMe	H	OH	H	H	OH
15.	OH	glc	OH	H	H	OH	OH	H

glc = β-D-glucose.

Sl. no.	C-5	C-6	C-7	C-8	C-8a	C-8b	C=O
1.	118.10	135.44	124.28	125.92	121.12	121.12	175.91
2.	117.98	136.39	124.53	125.36	119.83	108.28	181.69
3.	118.03	135.04	123.84	125.84	120.45	121.73	175.83
4.	117.81	134.68	124.03	125.83	121.25	114.08	174.74
5.	118.23	135.23	123.95	125.94	120.94	122.28	176.16
6.	117.61	135.52	124.28	125.18	119.84	102.25	179.73
7.	146.15	120.61	124.06	114.60	120.95	102.20	180.17
8.	102.07	164.23	113.98	127.16	112.28	101.69	179.10
9.	118.90	124.43	153.94	108.05	120.43	101.98	183.41
10.	107.02	137.13	110.54	160.29	106.87	101.14	179.69
11.	132.48	151.92	113.09	115.93	113.09	101.48	178.94
12.	102.72	154.03	143.75	108.16	111.89	101.65	184.26
13.	106.01	124.21	140.56	147.11	107.38	101.76	183.91
14.	137.32	123.73	109.35	151.83	107.35	101.98	179.20
15 ^a	102.73	154.11	143.80	108.21	111.85	101.43	

^aCompound corresponds to Sl. no. in Table 9.
^aAdditional signals due to glucose carbons at 81.61 (C-1), 79.07 (C-5), 73.14 (C-2), 70.72/70.45 (C-3/4) and 61.61 ppm (C-6).

Sen *et al*^{124,126} studied the CMR shielding data for a number of polyoxygenated natural xanthones

TABLE 11—SUBSTITUTION PATTERN OF METHOXYXANTHONES (126)

Sl. no.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	R ⁵	R ⁶	R ⁷	R ⁸
1.	H	OMe	H	H	H	H	H	H
2.	OMe	OMe	H	H	H	H	H	H
3.	OMe	OMe	OMe	H	H	H	H	H
4.	OMe	OMe	H	OMe	H	H	H	H
5.	OMe	OMe	H	H	OMe	OMe	H	H
6.	OMe	OMe	H	H	H	H	H	OMe
7.	OMe	OMe	OMe	OMe	H	H	H	H
8.	OMe	OMe	H	OMe	OMe	OMe	OMe	H

TABLE 12—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFT (ppm) DATA OF POLYMETHOXYXANTHONES

	1*	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
C-1	128.06	161.75	161.78	161.70	161.75	161.41	161.81	161.75
C-2	113.03	94.85	95.33	94.83	94.85	94.82	95.15	94.93
C-3	164.93	164.64	164.73	164.26 ^a	164.56	163.91	164.58	164.93
C-4	100.07	92.50	92.80	92.60	92.45	91.84	92.91	92.53
C-4a	157.89	159.50	159.45	159.56	159.62	158.24	159.66	159.61
C-4b	156.04	154.67	145.08	156.36	149.45	156.63	149.10	150.68
C-5	117.50	116.64	147.82	99.35	118.06	108.76	135.69	98.83
C-6	134.04	133.34	114.38	163.93 ^a	122.94	133.13	156.46	154.29
C-7	123.66	123.45	123.07	112.31	155.79	105.58	108.20	146.43
C-8	126.45	126.42	117.61	127.91	104.40	160.15	121.97	105.81
C-8a	121.82	122.84	123.94	116.72	123.26	113.84	117.86	115.94
C-8b	115.66	107.03	107.22	106.94	106.77	108.19	106.69	106.88
C=O	176.01	174.91	175.03	174.78	174.95	174.89	174.70	174.41

* Indicates compound corresponding to Sl. no. in Table 11. ^aSignals may be interchanged.

19, 20, 22, 63, 65, 127. The CMR data of some of the compounds had been reported earlier. The assignment are shown in Tables 13 and 14.

 TABLE 13—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF 22, 71 AND 127 IN ppm (± 0.05) DOWNFIELD FROM TMS IN CDCl₃ SOLUTION AND ¹³C—¹H ONE BOND COUPLING OF 127 IN Hz (± 2)*

Carbon	22	127	J	71
C-2	77.8	77.8		77.9–78.4
C-3	126.9	126.9 ^{db}	164	115.8
C-4	115.6	115.6 ^{db}	168	127.0–128.4
C-4a	104.4	104.3		104.1
C-5	157.8 ^a	157.8 ^a		160.2
C-5a	103.6	103.7		104.1
C-6	181.8	181.8		183.2
C-6a	112.1	111.7		118.7
C-7	136.9	137.0		115.8
C-8	142.7	143.9		153.5
C-9	154.5 ^a	158.0 ^a		122.8
C-10	101.6	98.2 ^d	164	118.7
C-10a	155.6 ^a	155.2 ^a		151.7
C-11a	156.1 ^a	156.0 ^a		156.0
C-12	94.0	93.8 ^d	167	94.0
C-12a	159.8 ^a	159.5 ^a		158.0
C-2(Me)	28.3	28.2 ^q	127	28.4
C-8(OMe)	61.8	60.8 ^q	144	56.7
C-9(OMe)		55.9 ^q	146	
C-1'	26.5 ^a	26.0 ^t	130	25.8
C-2'	123.1 ^b	123.1 ^{dm}	158	115.8
C-3'	131.8	131.5		131.9
C-4'	18.1	18.1 ^q	125	18.1
C-3'(Me)	25.6 ^a	25.8 ^q	125	25.0

*For other xanthones given in Ref. no. 204.

^aTentative assignment. ^bFine structure in off resonance spectra.

Recently, Maes and Steyn¹⁵⁰ isolated three interesting complex xanthone derivatives, sterigmatocystin (128), isosterigmatocystin (129) and 3,8-dihydroxy-4-(2,3-dihydroxy-1-hydroxymethylpropyl)-1-methoxyxanthone (130) from the cultures of *Bipolaris sorokiniana*. The carbon chemical shifts of the above mentioned compounds have been studied and the assignments are given in the Table 15.

TABLE 14—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF 19, 20, 63 AND 65 IN ppm (± 0.05) DOWNFIELD FROM TMS IN DMSO- d_6 SOLUTION

Carbon	63	65	20	Carbon	19
C-1	159.9	159.9	160.0	C-11	159.7
C-2	109.7	109.4	109.3	C-10	109.7
C-3	162.3	162.1	162.0	C-9	162.4
C-4	92.3	92.1	92.1	C-1	92.4
C-4a	154.2	154.3	154.3	C-7a	154.3
C-5	101.8	100.2	100.1	C-6	102.7
C-6	156.9	152.5	152.5	C-5	153.2
C-7	143.4	140.8	140.8	C-4a	138.1
C-8	136.4	127.7	129.9	C-12b	119.7
C-8a	110.1	110.1	110.3	C-12a	106.8
C-9	181.3	181.6	181.7	C-12	181.5
C-9a	101.9	102.1	102.0	C-11a	102.1
C-10a	154.6	152.0	152.1	C-6a	152.3
C-11	21.0	21.2	21.1	C-15	21.0
C-12	122.7	122.7	122.7	C-16	122.5
C-13	130.3	130.3	130.4	C-17	130.4
C-14	25.6	25.7	25.6	C-18	25.6
C-15	17.7	17.8	17.8	C-19	17.8
C-16	25.8	25.5	22.1	C-1	120.4
C-17	123.8	123.8	(No)	C-2	132.5
C-18	130.3	130.1	69.4	C-3	75.1
C-19	25.6	25.7	29.2	C-13	26.8
C-20	18.1	18.2	29.2	C-14	26.8
7-OMe	60.2				

(No)=Not observed (coincides with the solvent peak).

16, those for the side-chain carbons of 130a and 131 on the relevant formulae.

* Signal Obscured

(132) R = H

(133) R = Me

TABLE 15—CMR (125.76 MHz) DATA* FOR STERIGMATOCYSTIN (128), ISOSTERIGMATOCYSTIN (129) AND 3,8-DIHYDROXY-4-(2,3-DIHYDROXY-1-HYDROXYMETHYL)PROPYL-1-METHOXYXANTHONE (130)

Carbon	128 c^e	129 c^b	$J(C,H)$ (Hz)	130 c^a
C-1	181.08s	180.38s		183.21s
C-2	108.87s	107.88s		109.53s ^d
C-3	162.22s	161.05s		165.63s ^e
C-4	111.10d	109.99d	163.1	111.26d
C-5	135.48d	134.61d	161.2	136.89d
C-6	105.78d	105.95d	166.6	107.36d
C-7	154.83s	154.34s		159.31s ^f
C-8	153.87s	155.41s		156.39s ^f
C-9	106.46s	100.10s		106.46s ^d
C-10	164.45s	162.05s		162.85s ^e
C-11	90.43d	95.54d	162.0	97.86d
C-12	163.17s	159.86s		162.22s ^e
C-13	105.85s	103.79s		105.67s ^d
C-14	113.22d	142.12d	207.4	62.30t
C-15	47.98d	115.13s		42.03d
C-16	102.43d	112.24d	177.1	72.67d
C-17	145.25d	141.48d	203.4	66.02t
C-18	56.67q	55.74q	145.2	56.46q

* δ_c in ppm relative to Me_4Si : Letters refer to the pattern resulting from one-bond (C, H) coupling, s=singlet, d=doublet, t=triplet, q=quartet; solvent: ^a $CDCl_3$, ^bDMSO- d_6 , ^c CD_3OD . The numbering system differs from that used for the name (shown in structure 130) for case of comparison with compound 128 and 129; ^{d-f} signals may be interchanged.

TABLE 16—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFT (ppm) DATA OF XANTHONES 130a, 131, 132 AND 133

	130a ^a	131 ^b	132 ^c	133 ^c
C-1	162.9	163.4	163.1	161.7
C-2	97.7	96.7	98.1	95.0
C-3	164.5	165.5	165.1	(164.3)
C-4	92.9	91.5	94.1	92.6
C-5	101.7	98.2	102.9	95.5
C-6	156.9	158.1	164.1	(164.0)
C-7	143.3	144.0	113.9	112.4
C-8	136.4	137.1	127.1	128.1
C-9	181.1	181.7	179.2	174.6
C-4a	156.3	156.5	157.1	159.6
C-8a	109.8	112.7	112.6	116.8
C-9a	102.0	103.8	102.9	(d)
C-10a	154.5	155.3	157.1	156.4
OMe	60.0		55.5 (C-6)	
		55.6	60.8 (C-7)	56.1
			55.9 (C-3)	

^aIn DMSO- d_6 , ^bIn $CDCl_3$, ^cData from literature; Assignments in parentheses may be interchanged. (d)=Signal unobserved.

Lee and Ng^{18,19} reported CMR spectral data for several polyoxygenated xanthenes containing geranyl side-chain. A comparative chart of the carbon shifts for the xanthone ring systems of 130a, 131, 132 and 133 are demonstrated in Table

Sakamoto *et al.*¹¹⁸ studied carbon chemical shifts of a number of 1,3,5,8-tetraoxygenated xanthenes, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 of which 1, 2 and 4 are glucopyranosyl derivatives (Table 17). Carbon signal assignment have been shown in Table 18. Glycosylation of phenolic hydroxyl group results in the downfield shift of the carbon resonance due to the *ortho*- and *para*-carbons^{139,140}. While passing through the range from 3 to 2, signals due to C_6 ,

C₈- and C_{10a} were found to be deshielded by 2.1—2.6 ppm while other signals remained almost unaffected.

TABLE 17—1,3,5,8-TETRAOXYGENATED XANTHONES (134)

Sl. no.	(C ₁ -)R ₁	(C ₃ -)R ₂	(C ₅ -)R ₃	(C ₈ -)R ₄
1	H	Me	H	glc
2	H	Me	glc	H
3	H	Me	H	H
4	H	H	H	glc
5	H	H	H	H

glc: β -glucopyranosyl.

Structures of the newly isolated prenylated xanthones isocowanin (25) and isocowanol (26) have been confirmed from study of the CMR chemical shifts of the compounds by Ampofo and Waterman^{12a} (Table 19). They have also presented the CMR chemical shifts data of rubraxanthone (14).

 TABLE 18—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS IN ppm (DMSO-d₆)

Carbon no.	1*	2*	3*	4*	5*
1	162.6	161.7	161.8	162.9	162.1
2	97.1	97.7	97.3	98.2	98.4
3	166.2	167.1	166.9	165.4	166.3
4	92.1	93.1	92.8	93.5	94.3
4a	156.3	157.3	157.2	156.4	157.3
10a	144.9	145.3	143.2	144.8	143.2
5	141.0	137.2	137.3	140.9	137.1
6	121.0	125.9	123.7	120.9	123.6
7	112.4	109.3	109.3	112.6	109.3
8	149.3	154.3	151.7	149.4	151.7
8a	111.8	107.3	107.4	111.9	107.3
9	180.9	183.7	183.9	180.7	183.5
9a	103.2	102.1	101.9	102.6	101.2
OMe	56.0	56.2	56.1		
G-1	103.4	102.3		103.4	
2	73.5	73.3		73.6	
3	76.0 ^a	76.5 ^a		76.1 ^a	
4	69.7	69.7		69.8	
5	77.4 ^a	77.2 ^a		77.5 ^a	
6	60.8	60.8		60.9	

*Compound correspond to Sl. no. in Table 17.

^aThese signals may be reversed in each column.

CMR chemical shifts (Table 20) of two newly isolated prenylated xanthones, xanthone V₁ (44) and xanthone V₂ (46) have been reported by Botta *et al.*^{13a} along with that of macluraxanthone (32).

Holker *et al.*^{20*} isolated tajixanthone (135) and shamixanthone (136) and studied their CMR spectra (Table 21).

TABLE 19—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (ppm) FOR XANTHONES 14, 25 AND THE METHYLATED DERIVATIVES OF 25 AND 26*

Carbon no.	14	25	25-OMe ₄	26-OMe ₄
1	165.4 ^a	162.7	—	—
2	98.8	98.3	90.5	90.7
3	164.9 ^a	162.5 ^a	—	—
4	93.8	106.4	—	—
4a	156.3 ^b	159.5	—	—
5	102.8	102.9	97.7	97.7
6	157.5	155.1 ^b	—	—
7	144.7	144.6	—	—
8	138.3	138.2	—	—
8a	112.0	111.8	—	—
9	182.7	183.1	—	—
9a	103.0	104.0	—	—
10a	156.5 ^b	156.4 ^b	—	—
1'	27.3	27.3	26.1	26.0
2'	124.8 ^c	124.1 ^c	124.1 ^a	125.8 ^a
3'	135.1	135.1	—	—
3'-Me	16.6	16.6	16.1	16.2
4'	40.2	40.4	39.6	39.8
5'	26.8	26.8	26.6	26.8
6'	125.2 ^c	125.2 ^c	123.9 ^a	124.6 ^a
7'	131.5	131.4 ^c	—	—
7'-(Me) ₂	17.7/25.8	17.7/25.8	17.6/25.7	17.5/25.5
1''	—	22.1	21.6	21.3 ^b
2''	—	123.5	122.2 ^a	124.0 ^a
3''	—	131.5 ^d	—	—
3''-Me	—	25.7	25.5	21.4 ^a
3''-Me or CH ₂ OH	—	18.1	18.1	61.7
OMe	61.4	61.5	60.7/56.2/ 55.8/55.7	60.7/56.3/ 55.9/55.8

*Resonances in the same column with the same superscript are interchangeable. Spectra of 14 and 25 were obtained at 62.5 MHz in Me₂CO-d₆ and those for the methylated xanthones at 90.56 MHz in CDCl₃.

TABLE 20—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS DATA (ppm) OF 32, 44 AND 46

Carbon no.	32*	44**	46†
1	157.7 ^a	158.2 ^a	157.9 ^a
2	103.9 ^b	104.6 ^b	104.6 ^b
3	155.3 ^a	154.5 ^a	154.7 ^a
4	112.5	108.0	107.9
4a	154.4 ^a	156.3 ^a	156.1 ^a
5a	145.6	146.8	142.9 ^c
5	132.5	133.0	133.9
6	151.3	151.9	141.8 ^c
7	112.7	114.3	146.1
8	115.3	117.2	96.1
8a	112.5	113.0	112.7
9	180.1	181.1	180.2
9a	102.1 ^b	102.9 ^b	103.2 ^b
11	114.9	115.3	116.1
12	127.1	127.1	127.8
13	77.5	79.2	78.3
14	27.1	29.1	28.2
15	27.1	29.1	28.2

*C-4 chain 40.3, 29.3, 29.3, 150.0, 107.2. **C-4 chain 21.7, 123.3, 131.2, 25.7, 17.9, OMe, 56.2. †C-4 chain 21.6, 123.3, 131.0, 25.7, 17.9.

In same column, signal having the same superscript may be interchanged.

TABLE 21—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (ppm) OF TAJIXANTHONE (135) AND SHAMIXANTHONE (136)

Carbon no.	135	136
1	152.3	152.1
2	109.7	109.3
3	136.4	135.9
4	114.8	118.4
5	118.7	118.7
6	137.8	137.6
7	149.0	148.8
8	120.6	120.5
9	108.7	108.7
10	159.7	159.2
11	151.4	151.5
12	116.4	116.4
13	183.6	183.6
14	28.5	27.4
15	63.0	121.3
16	58.5	132.6
17 ^a	19.0	17.9
18 ^a	24.7	25.7
19	64.3	64.4
20	44.8	44.9
21	142.0	142.1
22	111.8	111.8
23	22.4	22.5
24	17.3	17.3
25	63.0	63.0

^aAssignments may be reversed.

Castelao *et al.*¹³⁹ studied the CMR chemical shift of the xanthonolignoid kielcorin (97). In this connection, they used the CMR data of toxyloxanthone C (137) for interpretation of the spectra of kielcorin (Table 22).

TABLE 22—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (ppm) OF KIELCORIN (97) AND TOXYLOXANTHONE C (137) IN DMSO-d₆

Carbon no.	97	137
C-9a'	113.7	116.1
C-1'	96.4	165.0
C-2'	145.6	102.7
C-3'	139.4 ^a	157.8
C-4'	132.3	89.3
C-4a'	141.1 ^a	157.2
C-4b'	155.1	146.1
C-5'	117.9	132.4
C-6'	134.5	151.7
C-7'	124.1	113.1
C-8'	125.7	115.9
C-8a'	120.6	113.1
C=O	174.5	180.1
OMe(2')	55.6	—

^aSignals in vertical column may be interchanged.

Recently, Namura *et al.*¹³³ reported the CMR data of the newly isolated cudraxanthones A, B and C (41, 42, 43) along with thwaitesixanthone (57) and rheedixanthone A (24) whose assignments are given in Table 23.

TABLE 23—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS (ppm) FOR XANTHONES 24, 41, 42, 43 AND 57

Carbon no.	41	57	24	42	43
C-1	160.6	160.3	166.5	161.8	161.9
C-2	99.1	104.2	98.1	100.2	100.2
C-3	163.4	157.7	162.1	162.0	161.9
C-4	100.4	94.0	100.6	108.2	108.9
C-4a	154.6	156.5	159.5	155.2	155.2
C-4b	149.4	149.1	145.8	151.0	155.0
C-5	120.8	120.7	133.0	101.9	101.2
C-6	124.2	124.0	150.9	152.6	154.7
C-7	151.8	151.4	118.2	136.9	142.8
C-8	115.6	115.3	120.9	119.6	137.0
C-8a	119.0	119.8	113.4	109.0	111.8
C-9	181.5	183.1	179.5	182.8	182.3
C-9a	104.4	104.2	102.2	104.6	104.5
C-11	115.1	115.5	111.8	40.9	40.9
C-12	126.8	127.0	131.0	28.0	28.1
C-13	78.1	77.9	77.3	18.0	28.1
C-14	28.3	28.3	27.7	149.3	149.3
C-15	28.3	28.3	27.7	113.3	113.2
C-16	117.6	117.3	114.8	120.9	26.5
C-17	132.8	132.6	126.5	132.4	123.0
C-18	75.6	75.3	77.6	75.8	123.0
C-19	27.4	27.3	27.7	27.3	25.8
C-20	27.4	27.3	27.7	27.3	18.2
C-7-OMe					62.1

The CMR data of the newly isolated xanthones, rheedixanthone A (24) and B (34) have been reported by Monache *et al.*¹³⁰. The authors also presented the CMR data of the reaction products (138, 139 and 140) of rheedixanthone B along with that of macluraxanthone (32) and manglexanthone 140 (Table 24).

TABLE 24—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS* (ppm) FOR XANTHONES 24, 32, 33, 34, 138, 139 AND 140

Carbon no.	32	34	138	139	140	24	33
C-1	157.7 ^d	163.7 ^d	165.1 ^d	155.6	159.2	166.5	159.4
C-2	103.9 ^e	111.4	92.8	100.0	115.2 ^e	98.1	103.5 ^e
C-3	155.3 ^d	161.9 ^d	163.3 ^d	160.9	158.2 ^d	162.1 ^d	156.4 ^d
C-4	112.5	112.9 ^e	112.6	116.2	114.5 ^e	100.6	94.3
C-4a	154.4 ^d	150.6	152.3	152.8	152.3	159.5 ^d	156.5 ^d
C-4b	145.6	145.8	145.9	145.0	145.4	145.8	147.4 ^f
C-5	132.5	132.5	132.6	132.3	132.3	133.0	123.1
C-6	151.3	151.7	152.0	150.2	150.6	150.9	152.2
C-7	112.7	112.6	112.7	112.0	111.9	118.2	147.7 ^f
C-8	115.3	116.1	115.9	116.1	115.9	120.9	107.1
C-8a	112.5	113.1 ^e	113.0	112.1	113.9 ^e	113.4	115.5
C-9	180.1	180.1	179.6	173.4	173.1	179.5	179.4
C-9a	102.1	102.3	102.2	105.6	102.4	102.2	102.3 ^e
C-11	114.9	42.8	43.2	44.0	43.0 ^f	111.8	114.5
C-12	127.1	89.3	90.3	90.2	90.2 ^a	131.0	127.8
C-13	77.5	20.8	21.0	21.5	21.0 ^h	77.3 ^e	78.1
C-14	27.1	15.2	25.1	25.6	25.1 ⁱ	27.7	28.0
C-15	27.1	14.2	14.1	14.3	14.3 ^j	27.7	28.0
C-16	40.3	40.2	—	16.5	43.3 ^f	114.8	22.6
C-17	29.3	28.3	—	30.5	90.6 ^g	126.5	121.6
C-18	29.3	28.3	—	75.2	21.3 ^h	77.6 ^e	130.5
C-19	150.0	148.1	—	26.6	25.4 ⁱ	27.7	25.5
C-20	107.2	108.4	—	26.6	14.4 ^f	27.7	17.8

*Chemical shifts in relative to SiMe₄, ^aSolvent [²H₆] DMSO unless otherwise noted; ^bIn [²H₆] DMSO—CDCl₃ (1 : 1).
 (OMe) at 60.3. Superscripts *d, e, f, g, h, i, j* in the same column, signals having the same letter may be interchanged.

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